

STUDY OF COCCIDIA (ACROEIMERIA LINERI) IN HEMIDACTYLUS FRENATUS (HOUSE GECKO)

BHIMRAO N. JADHAV* & ARCHANA SHETE

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Abstract

Coccidia are seen in all the species of reptilians and invade intestinal wall and heaviest infection shows the most significant clinical sign in all species. Phylum Apicomplexa of subkingdom protozoa is a large protest group composed by a diverse array of obligatory parasites. The aim of present study is to record Eimeria from common or Asian house Gecko. During the period of four months i.e. from June 2024 to September 2024, 45 fecal Samples (wet fecal material from field/ habitat) of Hemidactylus frenatus, common or Asian house Gecko were collected from urban area of Vaijapur taluka of Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar. 14 samples were positive for coccidial infection and percentage prevalence being 26.66%. In our study, we recorded previously described Eimeria species i.e. Acroeimeria lineri.

Keywords: Asian house Gecko, Eimeria, Coccidia, Acroeimeria lineri etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

In India, six different species of wild rabbit existing but Reptiles, particularly Geckos are most invasive species in world, Hemidactylus frenatus, common or Asian house gecko is native to Southeast Asia, but found worldwide due to human introduction [1]. This is nocturnal species generally found in warmth and humid areas. It is generalist predator on small insects and spiders of house undoubtedly control insects in urban areas. Geckos of various species are sometime exploited for traditional medicine and the pet trade in some Asian countries [2].

Coccidia are seen in all the species of reptilians and invade intestinal wall and heaviest infection shows the most significant clinical sign in all species. Phylum Apicomplexa of subkingdom protozoa is a large protest group composed by a diverse array of obligatory parasites. It is estimated that only 0.1% for the diversity of this phylum been described [3].

There are sixteenth families of lizard among these Gekkonidae have been more studied for coccidian studies. 24 genres and 52 species have been evaluated for coccidia parasites and represent 13% of which are infected with Eimeria (Duszynski et al. 2000, 2021).

The aim of this study was to record the parasitic (protozoans or helminths) infection in the fecal samples of common or Asian house Gecko, collected from urban area of Vaijapur taluka. In our study, we recorded some helminths specially nematodes eggs along with Eimeria species i.e. Acroeimeria lineri.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

During the period of four months i.e. from June 2024 to September 2024, 45 fecal Samples (wet fecal material from field/ habitat) of Hemidactylus frenatus, common or Asian house Gecko were collected from urban area of Vaijapur taluka. Fecal material collected in plastic bottle and brought it in to laboratory for further process as early as possible for microscopic investigation. The material were poured in to clean cavity blocks and inspected for the presence of coccidia or other infection. Oocysts are separated from fecal material by sieving and centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The oocysts collected were spread out in shallow petri dish in 2.5% potassium dichromate solution for sporulation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the period of four months i.e. from June 2024 to September 2024, 45 fecal Samples were examined for coccidial infection out of which 14 were positive for coccidial infection. The percentage prevalence being 26.66%. The highest prevalence 41.17% were recorded in July and lowest 00 % in September. The prevalence of coccidia from study also carried out by other researchers i.e. Stillwater, Harries, McAllister (1988, 2017) from Oklahoma, Louisiana, Texas, Union country Arkanas. Paperna and Landsberg (1989a, 1989b) in Israel and South Africa, Daszak and Ball (1991) in Turkey, Abdel Baki et al. (2020) Giza Egypt. Paperna and Landsberg (1989b) recorded 100% (2/2) is highest prevalence in South Africa and Daszak and Ball (1991) recorded lowest 09% (1/11) in Turkey.

Prevalence

Table 1 Showing percentage prevalence of coccidia in *Hemidactylus frenatus* (house Gecko)

Months	Total Samples	Positive Samples	Negative samples	Prevalence percentage
June 2024	10	02	08	20.00
July 2024	17	07	10	41.17
August 2024	12	03	09	25.00
September 2024	06	00	06	00.00
Total	45	12	33	26.66

Figure 1 Showing percentage prevalence of coccidia in *Hemidactylus frenatus* (house Gecko)

Figure 2 Unsporulated oocyst of *Acroeimeria lineri*

Figure 3 Sporulated oocyst of *Acroeimeria lineri*

Description of the *Acroeimeria lineri*

The oocysts *Acroeimeria lineri* are broad and ovoid in shape oocyst wall is double layered, 1.2 μ m thick. Outer layer is thick without micropyle and micropylar cap. The unsporulated oocyst is broad and ovoid in shape and shows spherical to sub spherical sporoblast filling central portion of the oocysts. The sporulated oocyst shows the presence of polar granule at the anterior end near to the oocyst wall. Oocystic residuum is absent. The sporocysts are broad and slightly tapering at both the end without stieda body. Sporocystic residuum is absent. The sporozoites are banana shaped and carry refractile bodies.

The dimensions of the sporulated oocysts are as follows

- Length of the oocyst = 21.0 - 28.5 (23.4)
- Width of the oocyst = 19.0 - 22.0 (18.2)
- Length of the sporocyst = 8.2 - 10.2 (9.1)

- Width of the sporocyst = 5.1 - 7.0 (6.6)

Sporulation time

The sporulation time of the oocysts was 24-72 hr. which may varies according to environmental and geographic conditions

Comments

Various scholars from different corners of the world described Eimerian species from *hemidactylus frenatus* (house Gecko). In India, *Eimeria knowlesi* Bhatia, 1936, *Eimeria hemidactyli* Knowles and Das Gupta, 1935, *Eimeria flaviviridis* Setna and Bana, 1935, *Eimeria* sp. of Saratchandra and Narasimhamurti, 1981.

Out of India, *Eimeria boveroi* Carini and Pinto, 1926, *Eimeria rochalimai* Carini and Pinto, 1926, *Eimeria gekkonis* Tanabe, 1928, *Eimeria koidzumii* Matsubayasi, 1941, *Eimeria gehyrae* Cannon, 1967, *Eimeria japonicus* Bovee, 1971, *Eimeria michikoa* Bovee, 1971, *Eimeria cicaki* Else and Colley, 1975, *Eimeria brygooi* Upton and Barnard, 1987, *Eimeria bongaonensis* Sinha and Sinha, 1978, *Eimeria delalandii* Matuschka and Bannert, 1986, *Eimeria tarentolae* Matuschka and Bannert, 1986, *Eimeria helenlevineae* (Bray, 1984) Levine, 1988, *Eimeria lineri* McAllister, Upton, and Freed, 1988, *Eimeria dixonii* McAllister, Upton, and Boyer, 1990, *Eimeria furmani* Upton, Free, Burdick, and McAllister, 1990, *Eimeria phelsumae* Daszak and Ball, 1991, *Eimeria rangei* Upton, Freed, and Burdick, 1991, *Eimeria barnardi* Upton, Freed, and Burdick, 1992, *Eimeria pachybibrioni* Upton, Freed, and Burdick, 1992, *Eimeria frenatus* Upton, Hanley, and Case, 1994, *Eimeria gastrosauris* Paperna, 1994, *Eimeria simonkingi* Ball and Daszak, 1995, *Eimeria vittati* Ball and Daszak, 1995. Peter Daszak et al. (2009) recorded three new species from endangered *Phelsuma* sp. geckos from black river gorges national park Mauritius i.e. *Eimeria swinnertonae*, *Eimeria stebbinsi*, *Eimeria raleighi*. Chris T. McAllister et al. (2014) also recorded Four new species of coccidia (Apicomplexa: Eimeriidae) from Owen Stanley skins, *Papuascincus stanleyanus* (Sauria: Scincidae), from Papua New Guinea i.e. *Eimeria bursevi*, *Eimeria goldbergi*, *Eimeria boulengeri*, *Eimeria niuginiensis*.

The present species is clearly marked off from various above-mentioned species from various corner of the world but it shows close resemblance with some of above species. The shape and size of present species resemble with *Eimeria raleighi* (Peter Daszak et al. (2009)) (spherical to sub spherical, bilayer without micropyle and micropylar cap), *Eimeria boulengeri* McAllister et al. (spherical to slightly spheroidal, single layer wall, with one polar granule) but the size is comparatively smaller than that of *Eimeria raleighi* and *Eimeria boulengeri*. The present sporulated oocyst and *Eimeria boulengeri* shows only one polar granule whereas *Eimeria raleighi* has 4-5 polar granules. Sporocyst is sub spheroidal without stieda body. This feature altogether similar in other previously recorded species.

Present species shows maximum similarities with *Acroeimeria lineri* recorded by McAllister et al. (1988), Paperna and Landsberg (1989b), Abdel-Baki et al. (2020), Allison Bryant 2019.

Stillwater, Harries, McAllister (1988, 2017) from Oklahoma, Louisiana, Texas, Union country Arkansas. Paperna and Landsberg (1989a 1989b) in Israel and South Africa, Daszak and Ball (1991) in Turkey, Abdel Baki et al. (2020) Giza Egypt. So, we conclude that, the recorded species in this area is *Acroëimeria lineri*.

geckos, the mediterranean house gecko, *hemidactylus turcicus* and the tropical house gecko, *h. Mabouia* from the new world. Thesis submitted to Oklahoma State University. U.S.

Table 2 Recorded species in area

Author	locality	Host	Oocyst size	Sporocyst size	Year
McAllister et al.	Louisiana Texas US	<i>H. Turcicus</i>	24.8 x 19.5	9 x 7.8	1988
Paperna and Landsberg	Israel	<i>H. Turcicus</i>	23.3 x 19	9.8 x 7.8	1989
McAllister et al.	Arkansas	<i>H. Turcicus</i>	24.1 x 18.1	7.4 x 6.9	2017
Abdel Baki et al.	Giza Egypt	<i>H. Turcicus</i>	22.5 x 20	8.7 x 6.2	2020
Allison Bryant	Oklahoma US	<i>H. Turcicus</i>	25.6 x 18.8	8.4 x 7.4	2019
Present author	India	<i>H. frenatus</i>	23.4 x 18.2	9.8 x 6.6	2024

Conflict of interest

There is no any conflict of interest

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